

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 4

 Acceptance of papers **April, 2026**

Acceptance of papers

Published monthly

Topics

economics, technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

Digital Object Identifier

Visit the website t.me/scopus_IST2100

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

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THE IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: the article analyzes the impact of the tourism industry on the socioeconomic development of regions. It examines the definition and essence of the tourism industry, revealing its role and importance globally. It also proposes ways to develop it, taking into account the country's rich culture, history, traditions, and other attractions.

Key words: tourism industry, tourism potential, regional tourism development, socio-economic development, competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

The globalization of socio-economic processes in the world requires diversification of sectors and industries in the regions. Today, the development of the tourism industry in the world is one of the promising directions of regional policy. This, in turn, indicates that it is becoming one of the main tools for ensuring economic growth, job creation, sustainable consumption and production in the regions. In particular, the fact that the tourism industry accounts for 10 percent of the world's gross domestic product (GDP), 10 percent of employment (357 million jobs), and 31 percent of total exports is a clear proof of this.[1]

The tourism industry is one of the most important sectors of the modern economy, playing an important role in meeting the needs of the population and improving the quality of life. In addition, since tourism, unlike other sectors and branches of the economy, is an export-oriented sector, it does not lead to a decrease in natural resources and is a more stable sector in domestic and foreign markets than other sectors and branches.

In recent years, the tourism industry in Uzbekistan has become one of the most promising areas of socio-economic development. The rich cultural, historical and natural heritage of our country increases its potential and competitiveness in the development of the tourism industry. Therefore, the study of priority areas for the development of the tourism industry in the regions of Uzbekistan is an urgent task of great scientific and practical importance.

Uzbekistan attracts the attention of the whole world with its ancient historical and architectural monuments, rich nature and modern development. The Ichan-Kala complex in Khiva, the historical centers of Bukhara, Shakhrisabz and Samarkand are included in the UNESCO special list of "World Heritage Sites". The unique monuments and architectural structures in these cities have played an important role in the history of the country.

In particular, the city of Shakhrisabz has a 2,700-year-old history. Shakhrisabz is also known and famous throughout the world as the prestigious place where the great commander and statesman, patron of culture and art, Amir Temur, our grandfather, attained perfection. This city has been famous for its great scholars and poets, people of art and culture, skilled craftsmen, and artisans since ancient times. The unique architectural monuments and rare relics in its bosom clearly confirm this fact.[2]

Khorezm has another priceless treasure worth coveting. These are its magnificent historical monuments. The fact that the open-air city-museum complex «Ichan Qala» is included in the UNESCO list as a universal

treasure of humanity also confirms our opinion. Note that there are more than 260 cultural heritage sites in the region. And their history goes back several centuries. Without a doubt, they are a living history that, with their unique and beautiful architectural appearance, determines the unique place of not only Uzbekistan, but also the entire Central Asia in the world development.[3]

In recent years, Samarkand has become a political, economic, tourism and business center, a platform for many major international events, forums and conferences. The construction of the «Eternal City» complex, the development of more than 40 holy shrines, the reconstruction of the «Samarkand» international airport, and the opening of dozens of international brand hotels have brought the region's tourism potential to a new level.[4]

Bukhara has always amazed the world with its centuries-old historical monuments and antiquities. In the Bukhara region, 829 cultural heritage sites are under state protection: 287 archaeological sites, 508 architectural sites, 17 monumental sites and 17 places of interest. Ancient monuments such as the Great Minaret, the Ark, the Great Mosque, the Chor Minar, and Ismail Somoni are rare masterpieces of Central Asian architecture.

Today, as a result of Uzbekistan's wide opening to the world, the number of foreign tourists has exceeded 10 million, and the export of travel services has exceeded 3 billion dollars (compared to the corresponding period of 2024).[5]

According to the explanatory dictionary of economic terms, tourism (from the French «tour» - a tour, from the English «turn» - a visitor to another country or region) - refers to social, cultural and economic phenomena associated with the movement of people from their permanent place of residence, usually for the purpose of traveling and recreation.[6]

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 15, 2025 According to Decree No. PF-87 «On measures to increase the role and importance of tourism in the economy by sharply increasing the flow of tourists and rapidly expanding the scope of tourist services in 2025-2026», it is planned to organize trips of 15.8 million foreign tourists to the regions of the republic this year, increase the export of tourism services to 4 billion US dollars, organize trips of 40 million local tourists to the regions due to the development of domestic tourism, launch an additional 378 tour operators, build 108 new hotels, 375 family guest houses and 123 hostels in the regions of the republic, create 745 capsule and mountain houses, apart-hotels, modular hotels, and 12 tourist villages and tourist neighborhoods.[7]

LITERATURE REVIEW

The first manifestations of tourism date back to ancient times, while it was formed as a mass social reality in the middle of the 20th century. The socio-economic and technological development of the tourism industry has been studied by a number of researchers and, based on its specific objectives, is divided into four stages:[8] [9] [10] [11] [12]

first stage: The period up to the beginning of the 19th century is the emergence of the first forms of tourism;

second stage: The period from the end of the 19th century to the beginning of the 20th century is the emergence of the first specialized enterprises providing tourism services;

third stage: The period up to the middle of the 20th century is the beginning of the development of social tourism;

fourth step: The period from the middle of the 20th century to the present day is the development of the tourism industry, which encompasses an interdisciplinary complex of tourism products (goods, services).

In the early stages of the tourism industry's development, it was not considered an important sector of socio-economic activity, but over time, the sector developed and its economic importance increased. By the 1980s, clear understandings of the nature of tourism and its relationship with other socio-economic activities began to emerge.[13] By this time, economists began to recognize the importance of the tourism industry as an economic phenomenon in the development of the world and national economy.

At this point, the author considered it appropriate to cite some possible views of economists. In particular, M. Porter believes that in the tourism industry, not only the attractiveness of the region, but also the quality of the products (goods, services) offered and its infrastructure are important for the consumer.[14] J. Jackson and P. Murphy emphasize the need to open up opportunities for the development of local markets in the tourism industry, strengthen the interaction of business structures in the region, and apply a cluster approach.[15] O. Kohl believes that it is important to increase the competitiveness of regional and interconnected local tourism in domestic and foreign tourism markets in large cities.[16] O.I. Kapustina and G.A. Smirnova emphasize that the development of tourism in the regions requires a systemic approach to its impact on economic, socio-cultural, and environmental processes.[17]

National scientists believe that the development of the tourism sector and its high efficiency require the formation of a tourism industry in the national economy. In order to fully meet the needs of tourists, the tourism industry will provide primary services (transport, accommodation, catering) and, depending on the purpose of

the trip, special (cultural, entertainment, recreation) and additional services. This will constantly require the emergence of new types of activity in the sector and the development of related sectors, and will be the fourth. [18]

In our opinion, in modern conditions, the development of the tourism industry should focus on issues such as the region's socio-economic policy, competitiveness, investment attraction, infrastructure, finance, marketing, etc. Tourism is associated with traveling outside the place of permanent residence, visiting new and planned places, remote and remote areas, and traveling.[19]

In this context, it is necessary to study in depth the problems that arise in the development of the tourism industry and develop solutions. In particular, it is necessary to develop the following directions and improve the infrastructure of the country's tourism industry:

- medical, treatment and health tourism: here, support for health resorts and recreation areas (treatments with mineral waters, prevention of diseases in beautiful nature, introduction of modern types of treatment);
- business tourism: business trips, conferences, presentations, meetings, visits to professional, industrial exhibitions and forums;
- sports tourism: in this, organization of sports activities such as outdoor cycling, mountain climbing, running, skiing (popularization of skiing during winter holidays), horse riding (equestrian sports);
- environmental (ecological) tourism: organizing excursions such as trips to nature reserves, national parks, small towns;
- industrial tourism: here, getting acquainted with production processes;
- hospitality tourism: here, getting acquainted with national cuisine;
- tourism for recreational purposes: this includes walking in parks, forests, nature reserves, enjoying springs and mineral waters;
- cultural and educational tourism: this includes trips to museums, theaters, and architectural monuments, as well as participation in master classes on crafts;
- military-patriotic tourism: including tours to military history museums, monuments, training grounds, and familiarization with the country's heroes;
- youth tourism: participation in festivals and musical events;
- children's tourism: trips aimed at developing creative potential and organizing recreation within the educational programs of children and teenagers;
- water tourism: travel that includes traveling on rivers, lakes and seas;
- hiking tourism: hiking along special paths in mountains, forests, nature and enjoying beautiful natural landscapes;
- mountain tourism, including extreme sports and mountain climbing;
- scientific tourism: research visits and scientific expeditions aimed at studying scientific achievements, historical discoveries, unique natural phenomena;
- tourism to get acquainted with national customs and traditions: this includes getting to know and participating in the national culture, customs, traditions, and holidays of local peoples;
- rural tourism: this includes getting to know the living conditions in rural areas and participating in agricultural activities;
- green tourism: in this, environmental education and nature protection;
- Pilgrimage and religious tourism: in this, travel to holy places;
- hunting tourism: this means offering the opportunity to hunt in the wild.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the process of research, logical thinking, scientific observation, comparison, compilation of theoretical and practical materials, and systematic analysis methods were used in the study of information and theories related to the topic.

Analysis and results. The article presents the author's materials prepared based on data from the National Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the importance of the tourism industry in stabilizing socio-economic processes in the country and the current situation, as well as some views that are worth considering in the future.

The share of the tourism industry in GDP is 2 percent in 2020 and 2 percent in 2021 It grew by 2.2 percent in 2022, 2.6 percent in 2023, 4.7 percent in 2024, and is expected to grow by 5 percent in 2025, or 3 percentage points over the analysis period (Figure 1).[20]

Figure 1. Dynamics of the share of the tourism industry in GDP in 2020-2025, in percent

As a result of the large-scale work carried out in the country to develop the tourism industry, Uzbekistan will receive 1,501,000 people, 1,881,000 people in 2021, 5,232,000 people, 7,957,000 foreign tourists visited in 2024, and 15,800,000 foreign tourists are expected to visit in 2025 (Figure 2).[20]

Figure 2. Dynamics of tourists visiting the country in 2020-2025, thousand people

In 2020, 94.4% of tourists visited the country from the CIS, while 5.6% of tourists visited from other countries, and it is expected that in 2021 it will be 91.1% - 8.9%, in 2022 it will be 94.9% - 5.1%, in 2023 it will be 92.2% - 7.8%, in 2024 it will be 90.3% - 9.7%, and in 2025 it will be 89.6% - 10.4% (Figure 3). In 2020-2024, the number of tourists from the CIS increased by 53 times, and the number of foreign tourists from other countries increased by 92 times.[20]

Figure 3. Dynamics of foreign tourists visiting the country from the CIS and other countries in 2020-2025, in percent

It can be observed that in 2020-2025, tourism enterprises increased by 2.4 times, the number of tourists served by 2.1 million people, and tourism services sold by 672 thousand (Figure 4).[20]

Figure 4. Dynamics of tourism enterprises, services provided, and tourism services sold in the country in 2020-2025

By 2030, the share of the tourism industry in the country's GDP will increase from the current 3.5% to 7%, and the annual number of foreign tourists will increase from the current 10 million to 20 million people (Figure 5).[21]

Figure 5. The share of the tourism industry in the country's GDP in 2030 and the dynamics of foreign tourists visiting from the CIS and other countries

In particular, the flow of tourists with high paying capacity will be increased, the annual export volume of tourism services will be increased to over 6 billion US dollars, transport connections between tourist cities will be improved, the time spent on the road will be reduced by at least 3 times due to an increase in the number of domestic flights, the number of 4- and 5-star hotels will be doubled, the tourism potential of the republic will be fully utilized through the diversification of tourist services and products, a tourist brand of the country that will be widely recognized in the world will be created, and new tools will be introduced to popularize national tourism products.¹[21]

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

From the above studies, it can be concluded that the country has great potential for the development of the tourism industry, but at the same time, there are untapped opportunities. In this regard, in order to promote the tourism industry (goods, services) in the regions and achieve success, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

- development of infrastructures (transport, engineering, information, innovative, etc.) and offering modern solutions;
- elimination of administrative obstacles (simplification of entry-exit system, creation of a favorable investment environment);
- training personnel in the field, improving their knowledge, skills and qualifications;
- increasing and developing types of seasonal tourism industry;
- reduce the impact of the tourism industry on the environment and increase measures for its protection;
- development and implementation of brand-marketing strategies of the country based on effective advanced foreign experiences;

¹ Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-348 dated November 19, 2025 "On measures to organize the activities of the Tourism Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and accelerate the development of the tourism sector".

Thus, the tourism industry, through its development in the regions of Uzbekistan, can contribute to increasing the competitiveness of the national economy.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 4

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